

Neoplastic Breast Lesions A Histopathological Analysis from a Central Indian Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Breast cancer is a significant health concern globally, with varying prevalence and characteristics across different populations. This study aims to analyze the histomorphological spectrum of breast neoplasms in a central Indian tertiary care hospital, highlighting the distribution of benign and malignant lesions and associated demographic factors.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted from May 2022 to April 2024, involving patients presenting with breast lesions. Inclusion criteria included all patients with histopathologically confirmed breast neoplasms. Data were collected through clinical evaluations and histopathological examinations. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software version 25, employing descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and t-tests, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Out of 174 cases, 72.42% were benign, and 27.58% were malignant. The mean age for benign lesions was 25.56 years (SD 10.56), and for malignant lesions, it was 49.79 years (SD 13.38). Rural areas accounted for 90.80% of cases, while 9.19% were from urban areas. All male breast lesions were malignant, while 73.68% of female lesions were benign. The left breast was more commonly affected (47.13%) than the right (43.12%), with 9.77% being bilateral. The upper-outer quadrant was the most frequently involved (32.18%). Fibroadenoma was the most common benign lesion (76.19%), and infiltrating ductal carcinoma NOS was the most prevalent malignant lesion (54.17%).

Conclusion: The study underscores the higher prevalence of benign breast lesions and the significant rural-urban disparity in breast neoplasm cases. The findings highlight the need for targeted screening, early detection programs, and improved healthcare access, especially in rural areas. Further research is essential to enhance breast cancer management strategies.

Keywords: Breast Neoplasms, Histopathology, Benign Lesions, Malignant Lesions, Breast Cancer Screening.

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Introduction

Breast cancer remains a significant public health concern worldwide, being the most frequently diagnosed malignancy and the leading cause of cancer-related mortality among women [1]. In India, the incidence of breast cancer is rising, with estimates suggesting that over 162,000 new cases were diagnosed in 2018, accounting for nearly 14% of all cancer cases in women [2]. This surge is attributed to changes in lifestyle, reproductive behaviors, and increased life expectancy, reflecting broader epidemiological transitions occurring in the

country [3]. Histopathological analysis, a critical tool in diagnosing breast lesions, enables differentiation between benign and malignant tumors and provides essential prognostic information [4]. This method is indispensable for understanding the diverse nature of breast neoplasms, guiding treatment decisions, and improving patient outcomes [5]. Previous studies have shown that histopathological examination is fundamental in understanding the biological behavior of breast tumors and aids in the precise

classification of various neoplastic conditions [6]. Central India, with its unique demographic and socio-economic landscape, presents a valuable context for studying the patterns and outcomes of breast neoplasms. Previous studies have highlighted regional variations in the incidence and histopathological features of breast cancer, underscoring the importance of localized research to inform targeted interventions [7]. Specifically, Chhattisgarh, a state in central India, has seen an increase in breast cancer cases, reflecting broader national trends. Data from the Chhattisgarh Cancer Registry indicated an annual incidence rate of 24.4 per 100,000 women in 2018, with a notable rise in both urban and rural areas [8].

Furthermore, studies have shown that the age at diagnosis for breast cancer patients in India is significantly lower compared to Western countries, which has implications for screening and management strategies [9,10]. Lifestyle factors such as diet, physical activity, and reproductive history have been identified as significant risk factors influencing the incidence of breast cancer in this region [11,12]. Additionally, genetic predispositions and environmental exposures have also been suggested to play a role in the regional variations observed [13, 14].

This study aims to analyze the histopathological spectrum of breast neoplasms diagnosed at a central Indian tertiary care hospital. By examining a large cohort of patients, we aim to provide comprehensive data on the prevalence, age distribution, and histopathological features of benign and malignant breast lesions.

This information is expected to enhance our understanding of breast neoplasms in this region and contribute to the global body of knowledge on breast cancer epidemiology and pathology.

Materials and Methods:

This prospective observational study was conducted at a central Indian tertiary care hospital over two years, from May 2022 to April 2024 after obtaining permission from institutional ethical committee. The objective was to analyse the histomorphological spectrum of breast neoplasms,

focusing on their prevalence, age distribution, and characteristics.

Study Population and Selection Criteria

The study included patients of all ages and both genders who presented with breast lesions at the hospital and consented to participate in the study and undergo histopathological examination. Excluded from the study were patients with a prior history of breast cancer, those who had already received treatment for breast neoplasms before their visit to our hospital, and those who did not consent to participate.

Procedure

Data collection involved directly gathering information from patients presenting with breast lesions. Each patient underwent a detailed clinical evaluation, including history taking and physical examination, to document symptoms and clinical findings. Biopsy or surgical excision samples were collected from the patients and sent for histopathological examination. The tissue samples were processed using standard histopathological techniques: fixation in formalin, embedding in paraffin, sectioning, and staining with hematoxylin and eosin. Pathologists examined the slides to classify the lesions according to established histopathological criteria. Special stains and immunohistochemistry were used when necessary. Detailed records, including demographic details (age, gender, locality), clinical presentation, and histopathological findings, were maintained for each patient.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS software version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize categorical variables (e.g., type of breast lesion, gender distribution, laterality) with frequencies and percentages. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for continuous variables such as age. Chi-square tests were used for comparing categorical variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results:

Table 1: Distribution of benign and malignant breast lesions

Breast Lesions	Frequency	Percentage
Benign	126	72.42
Malignant	48	27.58

Table 1 presents the distribution of benign and malignant breast lesions among 174 cases analyzed. The majority of breast lesions were benign, accounting for 126 cases, which represents 72.42% of the total. In contrast, malignant breast lesions were observed in 48 cases, making up 27.58% of the total.

Table 2: Distribution of Age of benign and malignant breast lesions

Breast Lesions	Mean	SD
Benign	25.56	10.56
Malignant	49.79	13.38
Overall	32.24	15.73

Table 2 shows the age distribution for patients with benign and malignant breast lesions. The mean age for patients with benign breast lesions is 25.56 years, with a standard deviation (SD) of 10.56 years. For malignant breast lesions, the mean age is significantly higher at 49.79 years, with an SD of 13.38 years. When considering all breast lesions collectively, the overall mean age is 32.24 years, with an SD of 15.73 years.

Table 3: Distribution among rural and urban population

Locality	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	158	90.8
Urban	16	9.19

Table 3 illustrates the distribution of breast lesion cases among rural and urban populations. The majority of the cases, 158 out of 174 (90.80%), are from rural areas, while only 16 cases (9.19%) are from urban areas. This significant disparity indicates a higher prevalence of breast lesion cases in rural populations compared to urban populations in the study sample.

Table 4: Gender-wise categorization of neoplastic breast lesions

	Male		Female	
	Cases (n=3)	Percentage	Cases (n=171)	Percentage
Benign	0	0	126	73.68
Malignant	3	100	45	26.32
Total	3	100	171	100

Table 4 presents the gender-wise categorization of neoplastic breast lesions. Among the 3 male cases, all (100%) were diagnosed with malignant breast lesions, and none had benign lesions. In contrast, out of 171 female cases, 126 (73.68%) were diagnosed with benign lesions, and 45 (26.32%) had malignant lesions.

Table 5: Distribution according to laterality

Side	No. of cases (n=174)	Percentage
Right	75	43.12
Left	82	47.13
Bilateral	17	9.77

Table 5 shows the distribution of breast lesions according to laterality among the 174 cases studied. The left breast was affected in 82 cases (47.13%), making it the most commonly affected side. The right breast was affected in 75 cases (43.12%). Bilateral breast lesions, where both breasts were involved, were observed in 17 cases (9.77%).

Table 6: Involvement of Quadrant of all neoplastic breast lesions

Quadrant	No. of cases (n=174)	Percentage
Upper-outer	56	32.18
Upper-inner	42	24.14
Lower-outer	32	18.3
Lower- inner	14	8.04
Central	13	7.47
Multiple quadrant	17	9.77

Table 6 details the involvement of breast quadrants in neoplastic lesions among the 174 cases studied. The upper-outer quadrant was the most frequently involved, with 56 cases (32.18%), followed by the upper-inner quadrant with 42 cases (24.14%). The

lower-outer quadrant was affected in 32 cases (18.39%), and the lower-inner quadrant in 14 cases (8.04%). The central quadrant was involved in 13 cases (7.47%). Additionally, multiple quadrants were involved in 17 cases (9.77%).

Table 7: Histomorphological distribution of benign breast lesions

Benign Lesions	No. of cases (n = 126)	Percentage
Fibroadenoma		
• Fibroadenoma	96	76.19
• Fibroadenoma with cystic changes	4	3.17

• Giant juvenile fibroadenoma	1	0.79
• Lactating adenoma	1	0.79
• Tubular Adenoma	2	1.59
Fibroadenosis		
• Fibroadenosis with cystic changes	3	2.38
• Fibrocystic disease of breast	3	2.38
• Sclerosing adenosis	1	0.79
• Florid usual ductal hyperplasia	1	0.79
• Adenomyoepithelial adenosis with fibrocystic changes	1	0.79
Phyllodes Tumor		
• Phyllodes tumor, benign	7	5.55
• Phyllodes tumor, borderline	3	2.38
Miscellaneous		
• Melanocytic acanthoma	1	0.79
• Lipoma	2	0.79

Table 7 shows the histomorphological distribution of 126 benign breast lesions. The most common lesion is fibroadenoma, accounting for 96 cases (76.19%), followed by fibroadenosis with various subtypes (9 cases, 7.13%). Phyllodes tumors are

present in 10 cases (7.93%), and miscellaneous benign lesions include melanocytic acanthoma and lipoma (3 cases, 1.58%). This indicates that fibroadenoma is the predominant benign breast lesion in this study.

Table 8: Histomorphological distribution of Malignant breast lesions (n=48)

Malignant Lesions	No. of cases (n = 48)	Percentage
Phyllodes Tumor		
• Phyllodes Tumor, Malignant	2	4.17
Invasive Breast Carcinoma		
• Infiltrating Ductal Carcinoma Nos (IDC Nos)	26	54.17
• IDC With Mucinous Type	1	2.08
• IDC With Pagetoid Dysplasia	1	2.08
• IDC With Medullary Features & Squamoid Differentiation	1	2.08
• Lobular Carcinoma	4	8.33
• Invasive Papillary Carcinoma	1	2.08
• Mucinous Carcinoma	1	2.08
• Medullary Carcinoma	2	4.17
• Apocrine Carcinoma	1	2.08
• Invasive Tubular Carcinoma	1	2.08
• Metaplastic Carcinoma	1	2.08
Ductal Carcinoma In Situ (DCIS)	1	2.08
Neuroendocrine Neoplasm		
• Neuroendocrine Carcinoma	1	2.08
Tumors of Nipple		
• Pagets Disease Of Breast	1	2.08
Smooth Muscle Tumors		
• Fibrosarcoma	1	2.08
Rare & Salivary Gland Type Tumors		
• Adenoid Cystic Carcinoma	1	2.08
Lymphoma	1	2.08

Table 8 provides the histomorphological distribution of 48 malignant breast lesions. The most common type is infiltrating ductal carcinoma NOS (IDC NOS) (Fig 1), which accounts for 26 cases (54.17%).

This is followed by lobular carcinoma (Fig 2) with 4 cases (8.33%) and medullary carcinoma with 2 cases (4.17%). Other types of invasive breast carcinomas, including mucinous (Fig 3), papillary (Fig

4), apocrine, tubular, and metaplastic carcinomas, each represent a smaller fraction (2.08% each).

Additionally, there are single cases (2.08% each) of rare tumors such as neuroendocrine carcinoma, Paget's disease of the breast (Fig 5), fibrosarcoma, adenoid cystic carcinoma, and lymphoma. Phyllodes tumor, malignant, is observed in 2 cases (4.17%). This distribution highlights the predominance of IDC NOS among malignant breast lesions,

with a variety of other less common types also present.

Figure 1: Photomicrograph of Invasive ductal carcinoma showing infiltrating tumor cells arranged in small sheets and small trabeculae infiltrating in between fibrovascular septa (H&E, 100x)

Figure 2: Photomicrograph of Lobular carcinoma showing monomorphic tumor cells having uniform round nuclei, prominent nucleoli and scanty cytoplasm with cells invading the stroma. Indian file arrangement of the tumor cells seen

Figure 3: Photomicrograph of Mucinous carcinoma showing tumor shows uniform epithelial clusters in large pools of extracellular mucin. The cohesive tumor cells form solid tubular or trabecular structures. According to WHO, pure MC requires a mucinous component of > 90% (H&E, 100x)

Figure 4: Photomicrograph of Mucinous carcinoma showing tumor shows uniform epithelial clusters in large pools of extracellular mucin. The cohesive tumor cells form solid tubular or trabecular structures. According to WHO, pure MC requires a mucinous component of > 90% (H&E, 100x)

Figure 5: Photomicrograph of Paget's disease showing epidermis infiltrated by malignant cells arranged singly or in groups, often more numerous in the basal region. There is associated chronic inflammation in the superficial dermis

Figure 6: Photomicrograph of Fibroadenoma showing biphasic or fibroepithelial neoplasm. The tumor shows intracanalicular pattern (compressed cleft-like ducts with stromal proliferation around glands) and pericanalicular pattern (glands retain open lumens but are separated by expanded stroma) (H&E, 100x)

Figure 7: Photomicrograph of Benign phyllodes show a biphasic fibroepithelial lesion characterized by leaf-like phyllode epithelial pattern, formed by an exaggerated intracanalicular pattern without stromal atypia seen

Discussion

The present study aimed to analyze the histomorphological spectrum of breast neoplasms at a central Indian tertiary care hospital, providing insights into the prevalence, age distribution, and characteristics of these lesions. The findings are consistent with several previous studies, and the discussion below compares our results with existing literature.

Distribution of Benign and Malignant Breast Lesions: In our study, 72.42% of breast lesions were benign, while 27.58% were malignant (Table 1). This distribution is similar to findings from other studies, such as the one by Kanchan et al., which reported a higher prevalence of benign lesions compared to malignant ones in an Indian population [7]. This indicates a general trend of benign breast lesions being more common, which aligns with global observations [6].

Age Distribution: The mean age for benign lesions was 25.56 years with an SD of 10.56, whereas for malignant lesions, it was 49.79 years with an SD of 13.38 (Table 2). These results align with the findings of Agarwal and Ramakant, who noted that breast cancer in Indian women tends to present at a younger age compared to Western populations [9]. The overall mean age in our study was 32.24 years with an SD of 15.73, reflecting the younger demographic of breast cancer patients in India [3]. This younger presentation age has significant implications for screening and early detection programs [16].

Rural vs. Urban Distribution: A significant majority of cases (90.80%) were from rural areas, while only 9.19% were from urban areas (Table 3). This distribution highlights the higher incidence and possibly lower access to early detection and treatment facilities in rural populations, consistent with observations by Malvia et al. [3]. This rural

predominance could be due to a combination of lifestyle factors, lack of awareness, and limited access to healthcare facilities in rural areas [17].

Gender Distribution: In our study, all male breast lesions (100%) were malignant, whereas 73.68% of female lesions were benign (Table 4). This underscores the rarity but severity of breast cancer in males, which has been similarly documented in the literature [18]. Male breast cancer, although rare, tends to have a poorer prognosis due to later stage at diagnosis and lack of awareness [19].

Laterality: The left breast was more commonly affected (47.13%) than the right (43.12%), with 9.77% of cases being bilateral (Table 5). This pattern is consistent with other studies that report a slight predominance of left-sided breast cancer [16]. The reason for this asymmetry is not well understood, but it may be related to anatomical or hormonal factors [5].

Quadrant Involvement: The upper-outer quadrant was the most commonly involved (32.18%), followed by the upper-inner quadrant (24.14%) (Table 6).

This is consistent with existing research indicating that the upper-outer quadrant is the most frequent site of breast cancer due to the higher density of breast tissue in this region [20]. This finding underscores the importance of thorough examination of this quadrant during clinical breast exams and imaging studies [21].

Histomorphological Distribution of Benign Lesions: Fibroadenoma (Fig 6) was the most common benign lesion (76.19%), followed by fibroadenosis and phyllodes tumors (Fig 7) (Table 7). This distribution is consistent with the findings of other studies, which also report fibroadenoma as the predominant benign breast lesion [22]. The presence of

various subtypes of fibroadenoma and fibroadenosis highlights the histological diversity of benign breast lesions [5].

Histomorphological Distribution of Malignant Lesions: Infiltrating ductal carcinoma NOS was the most common malignant lesion, accounting for 54.17% of cases, followed by lobular carcinoma (8.33%) and medullary carcinoma (4.17%) (Table 8). These findings align with global data, which identifies infiltrating ductal carcinoma as the most prevalent type of breast cancer [23]. The diversity of malignant breast lesions, including rarer types like neuroendocrine carcinoma and adenoid cystic carcinoma, reflects the complexity of breast cancer pathology [5].

Conclusion

This study provides a detailed analysis of breast neoplasms in a central Indian population, revealing a higher prevalence of benign lesions, particularly fibroadenoma, and highlighting infiltrating ductal carcinoma NOS as the most common malignant lesion. Malignant lesions were found in older patients compared to benign ones, with a significant rural predominance indicating potential healthcare disparities. All male breast lesions were malignant, emphasizing the rarity but seriousness of male breast cancer. The left breast and upper-outer quadrant were the most commonly affected sites. These findings underscore the need for targeted screening, early detection programs, and increased awareness, particularly in rural areas, to improve breast cancer management in India.

Future Recommendations: To improve breast cancer management in India, implement targeted screening and awareness programs, especially in rural areas. Enhance public education on symptoms and early detection. Improve healthcare infrastructure and training in rural areas. Conduct more research on male breast cancer and track long-term outcomes of neoplasms. Focus on analysing histopathological subtypes and invest in genetic and molecular research for better diagnostics and treatment. Advocate for supportive health policies and encourage collaboration between institutions for data sharing and comprehensive understanding.

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